

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDYING MEDIA TEXTS IN MODERN LINGUISTICS

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Annotation. *Initially, when theories of language learning appeared, hypotheses of its structure and origin were studied. The study of language by linguists revealed its other functions. It was found that each word is used in other meanings in the text in addition to its dictionary meaning. The author, who is well aware of these laws, can attract his audience with a high skill of choosing words and can exert his influence. The word has a certain meaning, and the text has a certain content. A student who knows the meaning of a word understands the meaning of the text. Understanding the meaning and content means understanding the text. Today, the study of media language, which has become a type of text, and its importance and features, has become an urgent issue. In this article, the lexical and semantic features of media texts are investigated.*

Key words: *media, text, media text, semantics, linguistic context, linguistics.*

Introduction.

The word "Medialinguistics" is formed from the combination of the words "media" and "linguistics", "media" is derived from the Latin language, meaning "middle layer", and the Latin word "medium" is the plural form of. The word "medium" is used in different meanings. It has the meaning of "carrier of information", therefore, the term "media" is used in relation to "information means". The word "linguistics" is derived from the Latin language and means "linguistics". "Medialinguistics" means "media linguistics".

Medialinguistics is related to the media and the activity of the language in the field of media, function and use of language in the media sphere with a comprehensive approach. In this regard, it differs from other new directions of linguistics. Medialinguistics is closely related to semiotics, that is, the direction that studies signs and symbols, because the language used in the media replaces symbols and signs and performs the function of conveying meaning.

The field of linguistics called "semantics" is the field that studies "meaning". He studies how language creates meaning. Semantics is the study not only of what a word means, but also of how words, phrases, and sentences combine to make meaning in language. Semantics, as a branch of linguistics, also studies the meaning of a word and how the meanings of the words in a sentence come together to form a common meaning.

Lexical-semantic analysis of Uzbek and English media texts

As a type of media texts, newspapers and magazines play an important role in human life, because they provide us with various local, national and international events and information. In order to attract the attention of readers, journalists use catchy, ambiguous words in the title of articles that encourage them to read the whole article. Also, when presenting information and events, reporters use words and phrases with different linguistic structures. It certainly depends on the reporter's choice of words. Below we will consider the syntactic and semantic analysis of the headlines of the articles of the newspaper "Uzbekiston ovozi" of Uzbekistan and "The Times" of Great Britain. As we know, a newspaper as a form of mass media is a reliable, reliable and transparent means of conveying information about local and international events covering all aspects of life, be it political or social. Only through the mass media, people can get information about events, political news, presidential decisions and other information. Also, people not only receive information, but also learn new words and expressions. People in society speak different dialects and are aware of the words that are entering the new language in the language of the mass media and the words that are used in it. This can be said to be one of the advantages of a printed newspaper from a linguistic point of view. According to linguist N.Tiono, language has an informational function, an expressive function, an aesthetic function, a guiding function, and a communicative function. In the mass media, the function of the language as an informant, that is, the function of conveying information, is used. When writing newspaper articles, the expressive function of language is used to express one's feelings and attitude to the events and events covered by the journalist using certain words.

In news reports, reporters use different linguistic devices and linguistic structures, even though they are covering the same story. We can clearly see this from the headlines of the newspapers. The newspaper headline is important to encourage people to buy the newspaper. The newspaper headline is read more than the article, readers will find out from the headline whether the article is worth reading or not. For this reason, the headlines of newspaper articles should be short, effective, memorable and able to attract the reader. Short and concise words are used to read quickly and fit into

a small space. The language of the newspaper headline is important in covering the incident. In the example below, we can see what artistic and linguistic elements journalists used in the articles and headlines of "Voice of Uzbekistan" and "The Times" newspapers.

"We need a strong anti-violence law"

("Voice of Uzbekistan" newspaper, issue 8 of 2023)

"How social mobility tripped on the red wall?" (Qanday qilib ijtimoiy tengsizlik qizil devor uzra sayoxat qila oldi?)

If we analyze the sentences given in these two titles, in both the titles of the articles, the author used short sentences and lexical tools with meaningful meaning to attract the reading of the article. Both articles are structurally different, but both are structured in simple sentences, unlike other headings. However, the reader cannot get complete information by reading both titles. When it is analyzed syntactically, the first title is T+A+E+K, that is, the first complement in the sentence, and the determiner is followed by possessive and participle.

In Uzbek, the parts of the sentence are usually placed as follows: the possessive is at the beginning of the sentence, and the participle is in the last position. , "*I told the story*", syntactic analysis shows that in the titles, sentence fragments are used in an unusual, rare and scientific language structure. When analyzed semantically, when the first headline is read, what kind of violence should be fought against, when did it happen, who did the violence, has it been fought before? , is the law established? , such questions will appear. In the sentence of the second title, the questions of what is social inequality and what is the red wall make the reader think. In Uzbek, the parts of the sentence are usually placed as follows: the possessive is at the beginning of the sentence, and the participle is in the last position. , "*I told the story*", syntactic analysis shows that in the titles, sentence fragments are used in an unusual, rare and scientific language structure. When analyzed semantically, when the first headline is read, what kind of violence should be fought against, when did it happen, who did the violence, has it been fought before? , is the law established? , such questions will appear. In the sentence of the second title, the questions of what is social inequality and what is the red wall make the reader think. When we analyzed semantically, when the first headline is read, what kind of violence should be fought against, when did it happen, who did the violence, has it been fought before? , is the law established? , such questions will appear. In the sentence of the second title, the questions of what is social inequality and what is the red wall make the reader think. In the sentence of the first title, we can see the denotative and connotative meanings of the words. The word "*violence*" in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language is "the conscious behavior of a person, which is the transfer of force and pressure to another person." This word is used in its meaning in the title. In order to show the meaning fully effectively, the pragmatic approach also helps in determining the purpose of the article by giving the relevant meaning. According to Galperin, although the title emphasizes

the main idea of the article, the second one should at the same time have its own style of language to convince the reader, and for this, the information published to him a reporter's personal assessment should be provided. It was seen in the above examples that the writer can use various stylistic devices such as speech marks and connectives, metaphor, rhetorical questions, emotional words to facilitate the interpretation of words and attract the attention of readers. German scientist Ungerer describes the essence of complex news in a few words. He described it as providing quick and accurate information and arousing the reader's interest. News headlines are especially important because they are the brain's system that controls attention, perception, and reading. An article is a key tool for interpretation and evaluation, and the title of the article is important as part of the overall information about the facts in the news article.

Another form of media texts are advertisements. Accuracy and effectiveness in advertising depend on the careful use of words. Words are used to convey meaning clearly and vividly to listeners and readers. As we know, there are two types of meanings, denotative and connotative. Denotative meaning is the word's own lexical meaning, and connotative is an evaluative, inferential or emotional meaning. Symbols are roughly the same for people using the same vocabulary, but words have different meanings for different people. Here, meanings are influenced by the context in which they are used, the relationship between the sender and receiver, and many other variables.

So, the denotation of a word is the exact literal meaning, and the connotation is the meaning associated with it. An ad that conveys meaning uses a wide range of words. Words often mean strength, reliability, excellence, fame, and other similar qualities. Advertising language is connotative. Below we will analyze the meaning of Coca Cola advertisement.

"To have a good time with your family, take a break, refresh and continue. Watch your favorite movie with Coca Cola."

With the family, take a break, refresh and pay attention to the words of your favorite movie. The advertiser tells the viewer that it is an ideal drink for the family, a refreshing drink when relaxing while watching a movie. The main purpose of advertising is to mediate the sale of a product. Marketers who understand this deeply attach great importance to the use of words in advertising.

Conclusion.

At that time, when the world is becoming a single media space, mass communication plays an important role in spreading information among people. As we know, language is the main tool of communication. Information is transmitted all over the world in hundreds of different languages. The language of mass communication is the texts in which information is developed. They are publicized in mass media. The main types of mass communication are: print, radio, television, internet and digital technology. The main task of mass media and communication tools is to inform, educate and entertain. The desire for newness, inherent in the nature of people, created

the need to translate information from different languages. Almost every country exchanges information with each other about events happening in the world. This process is accelerating due to the development of mass communication. When translating news texts, it is important to pay attention to the translation of the headline. The genre of news reports has its own discourse. Each genre forms its own speech structure, which is implemented in texts. The specific features of the translation of mass media texts are most clearly expressed in the titles, so they should be considered in more detail. In other words, the title should prepare the reader for the next article.

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